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Elevating the modern educational experience: Correlating ‘Practical Vedanta’ and ‘Bratacārī’

Dr Anusrita Mandal¹

Abstract

Vedantic thought and works of Swami Vivekananda and works of Bratacārī Gurusaday Dutt, were evolved to modify the human mind to reconstruct a developed society in India. Both of them deeply contributed to arouse nationalism on the spiritual aspect. This article made an effort to correlate the concept of ‘Practical Vedanta’ of ‘Swamiji’ and Bratacārī of ‘Guruji’ in the development of every individual. By the help of an Indian logic called “sthāthīpulākanyāya.” The present author tries to discuss the importance of Practical Vedanta through a cultural system called Bratacārī in modern education. Vedānta, Bratacārī and Modern Education will be the targeted area. In this context, the present author’s purpose is to recognise the value of Bratacārī as another form of Practical Vedanta in Modern Education.

Keywords

Bengal, Culture, Neo Vedanta, Spiritualism, Freedom, Bliss

Methodology

This paper is based on Primary and Secondary data mostly related to Swami Vivekananda’s writings and Gurusaday Dutta’s writings.

Objectives of the study

1. To know about the concept of Vedanta Philosophy
2. To know about ‘Practical Vedanta’ of Swami Vivekananda and ‘Bratacārī’ of Gurusaday Dutta
3. An attempt has been made to evaluate the significance of both

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for Modern Education.

Analysis

The concluding portion of the Veda is called Upaniṣad and another name of Upaniṣad is Vedānta (Amṛtatvānanda 3). Nature of a self or jīva is discussed in various Upaniṣads. Ignorance is the root cause of all sufferings of jīva. Another name of ignorance is bondage. When all types of bondage end, an individual achieves own self (ātmasurūpa) and gets enlightened (Muṇḍakopaniṣad, 2/2/83). Human being is not an isolated entity; rather it is a Cosmo-genetic element of the supreme reality. Upaniṣads elaborated the concept of absolute and all pervading (Ṛg Veda, 1/164/46).

The compound word 'Bratacārī' is derived from the Sanskrit root *vr*. In Bengali, there is no alveolar 'va' (*antastha* 'va'). So, from the very beginning it was written with Roman 'B' not 'V'. The present author has taken that spelling with diacritical marks. *Brata* means Vows and *cārī* means to follow, so the person who follows or performs vows they are called *Bratacārī*. The significance of the 'Bratacārī' is proved by its name. Dictionary has mentioned 'Bratacārī' as any meritorious act of devotion, the voluntary or vowed observance, any penance, fasting. In short, all are *Bratacārī* because everyone is performing some vows daily. Then what are the special vows here? They are knowledge, labour, truth, unity and joy or bliss. Thumb to the little finger of a hand respectively represents these vows. These five cannot be kept in separate compartments. Hence, we can find this open-handed gesture in all folk dances of India.

1. 0 What is the purpose of performing these vows daily? A lay man cannot perform subjective meditation (*antarmukhīsādhanā*) of himself, rather they believe in outer life (*bahirmukhīcāñcallyatā*). By this process of simplification, humans find happiness. Even in the ancient time of *Veda* and *Upaniṣad* the concept of *dharma* was spiritual and lived. But the definition of liberation has changed. Time goes on in the modern age that becomes ethical and in this case, 'Cultural'. It becomes a holistic approach towards freedom, life, knowledge, education and philosophy. The nature of 'culture' (OALD 370) or '*sanskṛti*' is dynamic and idealistic which is found in the human society.

Most of the cultural life of people is based on different folk literature, folk Arts, folk Music (song, dance, instrumental), socio-economic life with daily practices etc. Among all the means of the term 'Folk' the present author has taken the meaning 'informal'(OALD 600).

1. 1 In the early 20th century a new morality has come in front of us. By this time the society of our country was enriched by Western Philosophy and Natural Sciences. Some young scholars of native land were mechanically and blindly adopting the western thoughts. As a result, the 'Babu' Culture was arising. During the period of slavery of dependency under the feet of foreign European rule was painful which hurt the ego as Indians. They had marked that some of the western scholars started humiliating Ancient Indian wisdom. When India, rather Bengal, was under the colonial rule of British, there comes up an expectation to explain our scriptures in a new manner. As a natural reaction, they took vow to prove those scholars were wrong. This was possible because they were bathed simultaneously in both oriental and occidental wisdom. They were practical first and philosophical next.

1. 2 This is the idea of rediscovery of indigenous and invaluable treasure and counter attack at the same time on the foreign scholars. From the multi-dimensional spectrum, they added a synthetic and rational outlook towards Scriptures and revive classical thoughts and culture coming down for a long time. At this critical juncture, a new aura called the 'Renaissance' had started to spread its wings. Etymologically, 'Renaissance' means 'rebirth'. Some of them looked back with their tremendous intellectual dynamism towards Vedic wisdom. Among them in Bengal, Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo and Rabindranath Tagore were famous.

1. 3 As a Neo-Vedantin, Swamiji has sought to apply Vedanta Values. According to him, Practical Vedanta is not just a philosophy but it is a guideline for robust living for being fully human. He encouraged the practice of Advaita Vedanta in people's daily life linked with society. He said: "conceptions of the Vedanta must come out, must remain not only in the forest, not only in the cave, but they must come out to work at the bar and the bench, in the pulpit, and in the cottage of the poor

man, with the fisherman that are catching fish, and with the students that are studying” (Vivekananda 1998, 245). According to him “this Vedanta can be carried into our everyday life, the city life, the country life, the national life, and the home life of every nation” (Vivekananda 2009 342).

His Practical Vedanta was not only important in real life but it remains equally relevant forever. He modified Vedanta's philosophy in Practical Vedanta to increase the strength of the Indian masses. He preached Vedanta principles to use the Divine Power of an individual to free the motherland. So, with the help of Practical Vedanta, he tried to develop solidarity and oneness of the spirit by the elimination of social and caste evils in Indian society. He encouraged the practice of Advaita Vedanta in people's daily life linked with society, he preached spiritual stage through a humanistic stage, and in this process, he denied the evil practices by Indian priest class, Prince Class and trade class and sensitively responded towards the poverty and wretched conditions of working-class. He hated the practice of untouchability and laid a solid foundation for nationalism. He explored Indian philosophy and drew ethical Systems based on Advaita Vedanta, offering a solution for the salvation of humankind.

1. 4 At the very beginning of Indian freedom movement everyone was trying to define freedom as their own perspective. Swamiji also has done this. In that series, Gurusaday Dutt has come up with a new thought of National Movement called *Bratacārī*. Being an I. C. S. officer of the British Government in 1932, it was quite tough to start a movement against the ruler. At the very first stage it was created a sense of universality as well as national awareness (basically for India) through folk song, folk dance, folk art and crafts among people, irrespective of caste, religion, sex and age. It flourished as a movement to bring back our own culture to the masses. Then the question is why it should not be named as a Political National Freedom Movement? After achieving freedom, it should not be in existence. Even After his 80th death anniversary, what is the relevance of *Bratacārī*? *Bratacārī* is a formalised name of Undivided Bengal's Folk Culture. In 1935 after his lecture, in the International Folk Dance Festival at London *Bratacārī* Societies were created for Indian and English people both.

Even the philosophy of was extended over to Gujarat, Madras, Bihar, Assam and Delhi also.

1. 5 Usually Bengalis believed to be a non-martial race. He has done a cultural revolution and has changed the image of “*bhetobāngali*” into “*yoddhābāngali*” with the re-establishment of ‘*dhāli*’, ‘*rāibense*’ dance forms. As a result, *Rāibese* becomes a Martial Art of the nation from Bengal. The dance gathered into a single circle accompanied by vigorous clapping of the mouth of āwāwāwāwāwā sound with the right palm. The word *Rāi* means royal, king or kingly and *besé* means bamboo. Regional Folk dances and songs from another part of India like *rāsa*, *garvā*, *tiprī*, *bhānrā*, *koṇoṇīmachuyā* were adopted in the *Bratacārī*. It has made a mass consciousness all over India and aboard. It is a three-levelled improvement in all spheres of life like physical, mental and spiritual, which will create a complete philosophy of life within the person. Famous pledge of identification (*bhukti*) which a *Bratacārī* has to take as three declarations of enrolment -

“I love Bengal; I love Bharat; I love the World
I shall serve Bengal; I shall serve Bharat; I shall serve World;
I shall be a bratachari of Bengal, of Bharata and of the World.
” (Dutt 1989; 28)

1. 6 In other words, the aim is to attain the ideal value of a perfect citizen of the world. The essential part of the *Bratacārī* teaching is that before one can be a complete citizen of the world one must be a complete citizen of a particular regional unit or area. So, it is not just the matter of dance or song but it is the purification of a soul by the nurturing body and mind.

1. 7 Each *Bratacārī* has to practice many things throughout the whole life. Among them 16 more āli (action) are core. To know the gross entity at first one has to feel the ‘subtle’. One has to train the body and mind through *yama*, *niyama*, *asana*, *pranayama*, *pratyahara*, *dharana*, *dhyana*, *samadhi* (Vivekananda 1947 28) etc. to attain the highest level of mind. This comes under *sandhyānali*. Songs and dances are more regional and folkish in nature. This part is called *Nrityāli* where most of them are done to entertain and celebrate. War dance is performed in a circle accompanied with the *dhol*, *Kashi*, *Dhamsa*. In others *madol*, *dhak*, *gabū*, *ektara*, *jhajhi* etc. Instruments

are used. Songs are dynamic in nature. *Bāulis* included in that which consists of *rāga* and the regional influence. Here all can participate. Fundamental categories of Bengal's folk dances are: *sāmājika* (*Brata*, *Dhānbhānā*, *Jhumur*), *vīrarasātmak* (*Dhāli*, *Ran-pā*, *Rāibeśe*, *Lāthi*), *bhaktirasātmaka* (*Bāul*, *Mushidi*, *Kīrtan*), *sampradāyātmaka* (*Manasā*, *Gājan*, *Gambhīrā*), *ānuṣṭhānika* (*Jari*, *Dhamail*, *Megharānī*).

1. 8 The *Bratacārī* salutation or *abhivādana* way consists in uplifting the right hand with the palm facing in the front side. It indicates the highest reach of an individual's aspiration. To symbolically represent the five vows, one should keep his fingers tightly together in salutation.

2. 0 *Bratacārī* talks about the philosophy of self or atman just like *Vedānta*. It explains the true nature of a living being. A rhythm of oneness is heard in spite of diversity. As we all are different in region, language, caste, colour, gender but our goal is to attain the best part of our own self. *Upaniṣad* advises men to acquire the 'One' in many. *Bratacārī* conveys this theory in various song and dance like "nahabibhutumikabhuhinno he jagatjudiyātārchinho he". *Upaniṣad*said "tena tyaktenabhujīthā" (īśa. 1) means do not be greedy of anything since there is nothing in this world which is permanent and for which you may reasonably be greedy. "khidenāthākilekhaibonā" this line is fulfilling the same idea of 'need' through this.

2. 1 Till date, *Bratacārīs* from India and Bangladesh are participating in the full course training in *BratacārīGrām*, Kolkata every year. Here we can observe the harmony of the 'Undivided Bengal' beyond the political boundaries. One is not born a *Bratacārī*. After certain stages like *prāthamika*, *saṁkṣipta*, *mādhyamika* and *pūrṇāṅga* course an individual can get that level, but it is not the end rather the starting of a lifelong process in order to be a *Bratacārī*.

2. 2 So far, we have been confined in the theoretical aspect of AdvaitaVedanta but *Bratacārī* fulfils the practical aspect of that. It believes in the principle that all expansion leads to experience of bliss. The whole Veda is distinctively marked by the two heterogeneous characters- ritual (*kriyā*) and speculative (*jñāna*). Just like Practical Vedanta, *Bratacārī* has comprised both as the two main vows. At this stage it is said that, Brahman cannot be attained but after knowing the

Brahman someone can become *Brahman* (*Muṇḍakopaniṣad*, 3/2/9). In this case, it was also said “*Bratacārī* cannot be done” (Dutt 2004, 47), rather throughout life one should try to be a *Bratacārī*.

2. 3 There is a big gap between spiritual life and practical life. Notion has been broken by *Bratacārī* clearly. It creates a bridge between traditional and modern thoughts. The concept of *Brahman* is about equality where our mind becomes free from all bondages. The terms *Ji*, *Nāyaka*, *abhivādana* etc., are used in daily life. *Vedānta* is for all age, at anywhere *Bratacārī* is made for all at anywhere rationally. *Bratacārī* does not resemble the name of a relationship, rather a name with small designation called ‘Ji’ to each other. That is why Gurusaday Dutt is called “Guruji”. After completion of some stages he or she becomes *nāyaka* who can lead others in future. Swami Vivekananda’s practical *Vedānta* says, if a person of law realises *Vedānta* he or she can become an expert of Law. If a labourer starts to realise *Vedānta*, he will worship his work and that will lead to the development of society, the country and, therefore, humanity. With the deep respect towards the time and work, we will not humiliate ourselves rather we will happily perform any work. We have another line for that. “*mon jārchotōtār sob kājchoto hoi mon jārborotārkonokājchoto noi*”. World brotherhood, world peace, world unity, these are key in *Bratacārī* so it became a Vedantic revolution through culture. To achieve peace in the inner world, we have to remove our outer conflicts, problems and issues. Diversities will be there all the time. But we should not fight for those diversities; rather we have to accept and try to create a bonding among all the beings in order to peacefully coexist and walk together towards a destined goal.

2. 4 *Bratacārī* is a complex philosophical concept that contains much more than singing, dancing, doing various work. The core significance of the term *Bratacārī* is for self-realisation. It is true singing, dancing, exercise, handcraft work which occupied a central role in this but the philosophy promotes a liberal view. This philosophy emphasises love for all human beings. In modern education, some approaches which has been taken by *Bratacārī* can solve the problem of peace and harmony, political, social, theological and mystical problems.

2. 5 Besides all, *Bratacārī* have another important aspect about the concept of liberation. Although, it was mentioned when people were suffering under the British Government. But that is also for freedom. Independency of India cannot be done without Indian knowledge. The freedom cannot drown by the imitation of the Europe culture blindly. In Indian intellectual tradition, knowledge is not justified by degrees rather by wisdom. Independence from British is the outer part of freedom but the main cause of this dependency was *atmabirswaran*.

2. 6 The modern education which we are seeing today was the contribution of colonial power and Christian Missionaries. Mass education was not the mode of education as we see nowadays. Even women education was not considered necessary to women rather they were confined in home and their main business was considered to be child rearing. Women education was introduced by William Carrey and others in the 19th century. GurusadayDutt gave more emphasis on women education. He said, "mother's race should be liberated" (Dutt 1989; 42).

2. 7 Having all the body parts we are not human, in the same manner having so much degrees cannot justify knowledge. He re-defined education through many questions in his writing named "*morā śikṣā boli kāke*"? (Dutt 77) We are in a critical period where we are able to write in sophisticated English but we are unable to talk or write in our own mother tongue. Hence, we feel sorry when we cannot talk in English but we rarely feel sorry for not knowing our mother tongue. He has thought about 'man making education' (MME). Here the aim is not only to get pass marks or certificate but through practical knowledge person has to develop an ability to destroy all the impurities of body & mind. By the true heart & soul a person will work for himself and for others too. In various topics, even *Bratacārī* refused a mark of status called "*babu*" culture and said "*māṭhe col kodālhāte, cheḍe diye kolom ghaṣā*" (Dutt 49).

Conclusion

Through the lens of literature, the folk culture's life comes alive to us. In the *Bratacārī* a number of folk dances and songs of Bengal have been incorporated without modification of their traditional form. On

the basis of harmonisation of the Soul and Soil, Bratacārī leads us to our right destination. As a conclusion, it would be right to see that folk culture should be learnt by the people to save our Indian tradition. Folk and Classic are the two sides of one coin. Both seem contradictory but it can be seen as virodhābhāsa where one is structured and another is spontaneous. Regional culture and identity should be understood properly in order to gain a proper understanding of one's own self, and this self-realisation is the ultimate form of knowledge. Cultural intermixing of folk and classic has significant effects on the human mind. Bratacārī is that mixing product. If the sense of morality is enriched, human beings may give up all immoral activities such as rape, murder, kidnap, discrimination etc. Society is suffering from disparity regarding religion, caste, creed, and age, even from early 20th century to the present times, religions, different castes cannot tolerate each other, and many people are being assassinated for that. Politics, Economy, and Society all activities are full of violence. Most of our desires have been fulfilled but still our life is full of tension and we are not happy at all. Time has come to re-think again our own tradition so that we can make our best self. Enjoyment of ordinary pleasure of life does lead an individual anywhere and does help in any way in fulfilment of human journey. From the Vedic age to the modern era the cream knowledge of Upaniṣad accumulated in Bratacārī. Main idea of Bratacārī is based on three views- 1. Serve Humanity 2. Cultural Revolution 3. bring social oneness and equality in society. Therefore, he attempts to give a modern type to the philosophy of Vedānta that is realistic and necessary for human development irrespective of race, gender, caste, nationality and religious persuasion. Being an ICS officer, from the deep regard towards tradition, he can be marked as a Neo-Vedic seer like Vivekananda. He has accumulated all the definitions of education and has given a rational aim towards Swami Vivekananda's practical Vedānta through a structural institution called Bratacārī. This is one step further towards the bhakti and sufi movement, where bhogobān and khodā were worshipped together for the betterment of humanity. To conclude we must say that, Bratacārī is as relevant as our daily food for life. Tagore was deeply influenced

by Gurusaday Dutt. He wrote that,² Bratacārī is a way to be a human being. It is complementary to Vedānta and necessary to apply as a form of 'Practical Vedanta' in the modern education system.

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2 "May the Bratacārī movement soon spread through at the length and breadth of the country. I feel confident that whenever it is adopted, it will conduce to the development of Joy of spirit, capacity for work, strength of character and enthusiasm for social service." The Bratacārī Synthesis, p. 61

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